

Time series analysis and modelling of MIS-C cases: can we predict MIS-C cases by new cases in the 0–18 age group?

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Received 31 July 2025 ♦ Accepted 26 November 2025 ♦ Published 22 January 2026

Citation: Tomov L, Lazova S, Ali H, Miteva D, Tzotcheva I, Velikova T (2026) Time series analysis and modelling of MIS-C cases: can we predict MIS-C cases by new cases in the 0–18 age group? *Pharmacia* 73: 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e167298>

Abstract

Background: Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome in Children (MIS-C) is a rare but severe complication following SARS-CoV-2 infection. Early recognition and forecasting may support preparedness and clinical resource allocation.

Objective: We aimed to model the temporal relationship between COVID-19 incidence and MIS-C cases using time series analysis.

Materials and methods: We retrospectively analyzed data from 51 children with MIS-C (age 0–18 years) hospitalized in a single center between November 2020 and April 2021. A regression model with ARIMA(1,0,0) errors was applied to predict MIS-C cases based on weekly COVID-19 incidence in individuals aged 0–18 years.

Results: The majority of children were male ($n = 37$, 72.5%) and older than 5 years ($n = 40$, 78%), with a mean age of 8.82 ± 4.16 years. Abdominal symptoms were predominant ($n = 38$, 74%), and nearly half experienced respiratory ($n = 23$, 45%) or cardiac ($n = 26$, 51%) involvement. The ARIMA model identified a lag of 5–6 weeks between COVID-19 cases and MIS-C incidence ($R^2 = 0.41$). A selection-aware Monte Carlo simulation confirmed the robustness of the model's significant regressors when extrapolated beyond the original data period.

Conclusion: The moderate predictive power of the ARIMA model supports the potential of syndromic surveillance to forecast MIS-C clusters, aiding early intervention. Larger datasets could further enhance prediction accuracy.

Keywords

Age, children, COVID-19, MIS-C, modelling, prediction, SARS-CoV-2, time series analysis

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic, driven by SARS-CoV-2, disproportionately affected adults, but a delayed and serious pediatric complication soon emerged: multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C), a severe hyperinflammatory response emerging 2–6 weeks post infection. By June 2020, ~1000 MIS-C cases had emerged globally, often clinically resembling Kawasaki disease but with distinguishing features such as older age, myocardial dysfunction, and profound gastrointestinal involvement (Levin 2020; Stoyanova et al. 2025). MIS-C presents with persistent fever (>38 °C for ≥ 24 h), systemic inflammation (CRP > 30 mg/L), and multiorgan involvement. Distinct from Kawasaki disease, it predominantly affects older children (median age 8–11 years) who require ICU care admission, with the development of cardiac dysfunction (40.6%), shock (35.4%), and myocarditis (22.8%). Laboratory hallmarks include lymphopenia, thrombocytopenia, and elevated cardiac biomarkers (troponin, NT-proBNP), reflecting its unique post-COVID immunopathology characterized by IL-6/IL-10 dominance and endothelial injury (Lazova et al. 2023; Molloy et al. 2023).

After Italy's first COVID-19 wave in April 2020, the Rheumatology Study Group of the Italian Society of Pediatrics reported children diagnosed with MIS-C (La Torre et al. 2023). United States surveillance data from 2020 to 2023 recorded 9,370 MIS-C diagnoses and 76 deaths, corresponding to a case-fatality rate of 0.8% (CDC 2025). Independent multinational research conducted between 2020 and 2022 ($n = 1,009$) confirmed an identical mortality rate of 0.8%, demonstrating consistent outcomes across diverse populations (Caorsi et al. 2024). European epidemiological investigations initially reported a cumulative MIS-C incidence of 3.27 per 100,000 population, with a prevalence of 74 cases per 100,000 SARS-CoV-2–infected children aged 0–18 years (La Torre et al. 2023). Supporting these findings, a Bulgarian cohort study conducted between 2020 and 2022 ($n = 31$) reported that patients commonly presented with fever (median duration: 5 days), accompanied by characteristic mucocutaneous manifestations such as conjunctivitis and exanthema, gastrointestinal symptoms (70%), and cardiac involvement, particularly myocarditis (61%). Additional clinical features included serositis (51%), peripheral edema (28%), lymphadenitis (22%), and renal dysfunction (6%) (PReS 2022).

In epidemiology, statistical modeling and forecasting are crucial for understanding the underlying patterns and factors that drive the spread of infectious diseases, including conditions such as MIS-C that follow SARS-CoV-2 infection (Yadav and Akhter 2021). Time series analysis examines sequential temporal data to model system behavior. Prediction identifies intervariable relationships and correlations, while forecasting extrapolates future values using both historical trends and covariates through regression modeling (Tomov et al. 2023). Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) models are widely

used for time series forecasting, employing autoregressive and moving average components to predict future values from historical data (Kaushik et al. 2020). Time series analysis enables (1) disease surveillance (e.g., modeling COVID-19 trends); (2) clinical monitoring (e.g., detecting arrhythmias from ECG/EEG data); (3) prognostic modeling (e.g., predicting cancer progression from EHRs); and (4) resource optimization (e.g., forecasting hospital admissions). It also supports personalized medicine through continuous wearable data analysis (Aydin 2022).

Our time series analysis includes a retrospective observational study of a Bulgarian cohort of children with MIS-C, aiming to identify temporal dependencies between pediatric SARS-CoV-2 infections and subsequent MIS-C cases.

Materials and methods

Study subjects

This study was conducted between November 2020 and April 2021 and included 51 pediatric patients aged 0–18 years who were diagnosed with multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C) at a single tertiary university hospital in Bulgaria. The inclusion criterion was a confirmed diagnosis of MIS-C according to the clinical, laboratory, and epidemiological definitions jointly established by the World Health Organization (WHO 2020), the UK Royal College of Paediatrics and Child Health (RCPC), and the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC).

Patients who did not meet these criteria were excluded from the study.

All participants underwent systematic evaluation by a multidisciplinary team, including pediatricians, cardiologists, infectious disease specialists, and intensive care physicians, to ensure diagnostic accuracy and appropriate classification of disease severity.

Epidemiological methods

All enrolled children were hospitalized in the Pediatric Department of the main emergency hospital in Sofia, Bulgaria. Upon admission, a comprehensive medical history was obtained for each patient, including information on underlying conditions, confirmed or suspected COVID-19 infection within the previous two months, and any close contact with a confirmed COVID-19 case in the household.

Fever and abdominal pain were the most common presenting symptoms. All children with moderate to severe gastrointestinal manifestations such as abdominal pain, vomiting, nausea, or diarrhea were evaluated by pediatric surgeons during both the initial assessment and subsequent hospitalization.

In addition, all patients underwent a detailed physical examination and extensive laboratory and imaging evaluations, including hematological, serological, virological, microbiological, and radiological assessments.

These evaluations were conducted by a multidisciplinary team comprising pediatricians, pediatric surgeons, cardiologists, gastroenterologists, pulmonologists, intensive care specialists, and radiologists.

Statistical methods and analysis

To investigate the epidemiological characteristics of MIS-C, multiple statistical approaches were applied. Descriptive statistics were performed using Microsoft Excel, whereas data preparation and preliminary modeling, including multinomial logistic regression, paired t-testing, and linear regression, were conducted using the open-source platform GNU Octave (version 6.3.0; <https://www.gnu.org/software/octave/>).

Time series analyses were performed in R version 4.0.2 (R Core Team 2021) using RStudio. Logistic regression was used for the classification of binary or discrete outcome variables dependent on discrete or continuous predictors. Correlation analyses were conducted prior to multinomial regression, and principal component analysis was not required.

For temporal modeling, regression with ARIMA(1, 0, 0) errors was applied, with both MIS-C and COVID-19 cases aggregated on a weekly basis. The predictor variable consisted of newly reported COVID-19 cases among individuals aged 0–18 years, selected to represent the pediatric population at risk and the low baseline probability of MIS-C occurrence. A pronounced autoregressive component was identified, consistent with an approximate 5-week delay between SARS-CoV-2 infection and MIS-C symptom onset. The delay between symptom onset and hospitalization was modeled using a truncated normal distribution. Two patients exhibited extreme delays (> 12 SD above the mean); following statistical process control principles (Koronacki and Thompson 2001), these cases were evaluated as potential special-cause variations.

Time series stationarity was assessed using the Augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) test implemented through the `ndiffs()` function of the “urca” package (Dickey and Fuller 1979), confirming that zero-order differencing was sufficient for the weekly MIS-C series. Optimal ARIMA parameters were selected using the `auto.arima()` function from the forecast package based on the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC).

To assess the stability of the lagged regressors (MSC L5 and MSC L6), a selection-aware Monte Carlo simulation was conducted by extending the original time series by 12 to 52 weeks of simulated data. For each extended dataset, the regression model with ARIMA(1, 0, 0) errors was refitted under both a fixed specification and automatic model reselection using `auto.arima()`. The probability that a statistically significant regressor ($p < 0.05$) became nonsignificant ($p \geq 0.05$) was calculated across simulation replicates. As described in Suppl. material 1, the probability of significance loss for the key MSC L5 predictor was $\leq 0.6\%$ under model reselection and

$\leq 0.2\%$ under the fixed specification, indicating strong model robustness and parameter stability.

Results

Demographic, clinical, and epidemiological characteristics of the study patients

The majority of patients were male ($n = 37$, 72.5%) and over 5 years of age ($n = 40$, 78%), with a mean age of 8.82 ± 4.16 years. All enrolled children, except one, had a negative initial nasopharyngeal rapid antigen test; however, they demonstrated either SARS-CoV-2 seropositivity or a documented household contact with a confirmed COVID-19 case within the two months preceding admission, indicating prior infection. Nasopharyngeal PCR testing was performed in 26 children during the first six months of the study and yielded initially negative results; however, repeat PCR testing during hospitalization in two of these cases returned positive results.

Seventy-four percent of children ($n = 38$) presented with severe abdominal pain mimicking an acute abdomen, with appendicitis-like symptoms observed in 20%. Seven patients required surgical intervention, including five appendectomies and two thoracenteses performed for pleural effusion. Nearly half of the patients (45%) developed respiratory symptoms during hospitalization, while 51% exhibited cardiac involvement, with four children requiring intensive care for myocarditis-related shock or acute renal failure within 48 hours of admission. Of these patients, two required vasopressor and inotropic support, and one required continuous renal replacement therapy (CRRT). Treatment included fluid therapy, antibiotics, corticosteroids, anticoagulants, intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIG), and supportive care. All patients recovered completely and were discharged in good clinical condition; no fatalities were recorded.

Correlation between the onset of symptoms and hospital admission

A delay was observed between symptom onset and hospital admission. The mean delay was 5.33 ± 6.92 days (Fig. 1). Most patients were admitted within 2–7 days after symptom onset, with a peak at 4 days. A small number of outliers experienced delays exceeding 30 days, indicating variability in disease recognition or access to healthcare.

The distribution of delays was well fitted by a truncated normal distribution defined on $x \in [0, \infty)$, with $\mu = 4.02$ and $\sigma = 2.17$. Two exceptional values exhibited extremely small probabilities within this distribution [$\text{pdf}(35) \approx 1.67 \times 10^{-45}$]. One case involved prior admission to another pediatric department for suspected acute abdomen, whereas the other likely reflected reporting bias, in which acute COVID-19 symptoms overlapped with MIS-C manifestations without a symptom-free interval.

Figure 1. Histogram showing the time delay between symptom onset and hospital admission in children diagnosed with MIS-C.

Time series analysis and modeling of MIS-C cases

Regression with ARIMA errors was applied as a robust time series modeling approach using symptom onset dates aggregated on a weekly basis. Weekly MIS-C cases were regressed against weekly COVID-19 cases in the 0–18 age group. The time series spanned from the 23rd week of 2020 to the 7th week of 2022. In R, the series was defined as 52 weeks per year, with cases from the 53rd week of 2021 added to the 52nd week. The `auto.arima()` function was used to select the optimal ARIMA model (R Core Team 2021).

The Augmented Dickey–Fuller test (ADF) implemented in the “`ndiffs`” function of the “`urca`” package was used to verify that a model with zero differencing was appropriate. The test confirmed that the time series of weekly MIS-C cases required zero-order differencing to achieve stationarity and was therefore stationary (Dickey and Fuller 1979).

The resulting model is summarized in Table 1 and illustrated in Figs 2, 3. The model included an autoregressive term (AR1) and lagged variables for MIS-C incidence at lags 5 and 6 (MSC L5 and MSC L6). The estimated model coefficients were AR1 = 0.521 (SE = 0.093), MSC L5 = –0.00061 (SE = 0.00031), and MSC L6 = 0.00170 (SE = 0.00040). Model performance metrics were $R^2 = 0.410$, Bias = 0.053, and Mean Absolute Scaled Error (MASE) = 0.805.

The obtained model demonstrated well-estimated parameters with low standard errors and an $R^2 = 0.41$, which is encouraging given the small sample size. All coefficients had p -values ≤ 0.05 , with MSC L5 approaching the significance threshold. However, further analysis indicated that the risk of losing statistical significance for this coefficient was minimal.

Table 1. ARIMA model parameters for forecasting multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C) cases.

Model summary				
Coefficient	Estimate	Standard error	Coefficient	Significance, p
AR1	0.521	0.093	AR1	2.02×10^{-8}
MSC L5	–0.00061	0.00031	MSC L5	0.026 *
MSC L6	0.0017	0.00040	MSC L6	$1.65 \times 10^{-4****}$

$R^2 = 0.410$, Bias = 0.053, MASE = 0.805.

Using selection-aware Monte Carlo simulations tailored to the ARIMA(1, 0, 0) regression model, the probability that MSC L5 became nonsignificant after the addition of 12–52 weeks of data was $\leq 0.6\%$ under model reselection and $\leq 0.2\%$ under a fixed specification, with 95% upper bounds below 1.2% and 0.6%, respectively (Suppl. material 1).

An extended dataset could further improve predictive accuracy. Residuals were normally distributed and stationary (Fig. 2), indicating correct model specification. The optimal lag between infection and symptom onset was estimated to be 5–6 weeks. The combination of coefficients, including the negative MSC L5 term, provided a first approximation of 1.2 MIS-C cases per 1,000 new hospital cases during the first two waves. Expected rates for the Omicron variant are lower and will be analyzed after the current wave subsides.

Furthermore, longer hospital stays were associated with pancreatic injury in patients. This association was statistically significant ($p = 0.004$).

Discussion

Our time series analysis, using a regression framework with ARIMA(1, 0, 0) errors, demonstrates that the weekly incidence of MIS-C can be moderately predicted from the number of newly reported COVID-19 cases among children aged 0–18 years, particularly when accounting for a lag of approximately 5–6 weeks. The model yielded an R^2 value of 0.41, indicating a reasonable level of predictive accuracy given the limited sample size. Residual diagnostics supported model adequacy, confirming both normality and stationarity. Taken together, these findings suggest that syndromic surveillance of pediatric COVID-19 cases may function as an early warning tool for the emergence of MIS-C clusters. This has important public health implications, as MIS-C cases, although decreasing in frequency, remain clinically severe and continue to impose a substantial burden on healthcare systems (Carzaniga et al. 2025).

In earlier work, we demonstrated through ARIMA-based time series modeling that epidemic dynamics and excess mortality follow predictable causal patterns, with weekly COVID-19 incidence during the preceding two weeks and shifts in circulating viral variants explaining approximately 95% of observed excess mortality trends. That approach also identified latent mortality components not captured by routine surveillance indicators (Tomov et al. 2023).

Consistent with this prior work, the present time series analysis provides important insight into the temporal association between pediatric SARS-CoV-2 infections and the subsequent development of MIS-C. The moderate predictive performance of the ARIMA model ($R^2 = 0.41$) underscores the potential value of epidemiological surveillance data for anticipating MIS-C activity. In line with previous studies reporting a 4–6-week interval between population-level COVID-19 peaks and the onset of MIS-C, our model identified optimal predictive lags

Residuals from Regression with ARIMA(1,0,0) errors

Figure 2. Residuals from the ARIMA regression model showing normal distribution and stationarity, indicating that model assumptions are adequately met for reliable forecasting. Diagnostic plots of residuals from the regression model with ARIMA(1, 0, 0) errors are shown. The top panel presents the time series of residuals, indicating stationarity. The bottom left panel displays the autocorrelation function (ACF) of the residuals, suggesting no significant autocorrelation. The bottom right panel shows a histogram of residuals overlaid with a normal density curve, indicating approximate normality and good model fit.

Figure 3. Weekly observed versus predicted MIS-C cases using the fitted ARIMA(1, 0, 0) regression model. The red line represents observed MIS-C case counts, whereas the blue line shows the fitted values generated by the model. The model demonstrates moderate predictive performance, with an R^2 value of 0.41, capturing major trends and peaks in MIS-C incidence over the study period.

at 5 and 6 weeks. This delay is biologically plausible and reflects the postinfectious, immune-mediated nature of MIS-C pathogenesis (Cirks et al. 2021; Lopez et al. 2022).

The model coefficients, particularly the opposing directional effects of MSC L5 and MSC L6, likely capture the complex interplay among community infection dynamics, host immune response kinetics, and potential variability or delays in MIS-C reporting (Vella et al. 2021; Carzaniga et

al. 2025). Sensitivity analyses assessing the probability of MSC L5 and MSC L6 losing statistical significance under extended model iterations demonstrated a very low likelihood (<1%), further supporting the stability and robustness of the predictive model across plausible data extensions.

Despite these strengths, several limitations must be acknowledged. The dataset was relatively small and derived from a single center, which restricts external validity and may limit the model's ability to capture broader epidemiological heterogeneity. Future analyses incorporating larger, multicenter cohorts and additional predictors, such as circulating variant dynamics, vaccination uptake, socioeconomic or demographic modifiers, and environmental influences, would likely improve model precision and enhance predictive performance (Nirmalarajah et al. 2025).

The complete recovery of all patients, despite the severity of their clinical presentations, including appendicitis-like symptoms, significant cardiac involvement, and intensive care admissions, is encouraging and aligns with outcomes reported in other international cohorts (Abrams et al. 2020; Belhadjer et al. 2020; Garazzino et al. 2020; PICS 2020; Riphagen et al. 2020; Shroeder et al. 2020; Verdoni et al. 2020; Payne et al. 2021). Nevertheless, the substantial variability observed in the interval between symptom onset and hospital admission, with a mean delay of 5.33 days and a subset of patients presenting after more than 35–40 days, highlights ongoing challenges in early clinical recognition and timely referral (Abrams et al.

2021; Alvarado-Gamarra et al. 2023; Yamazaki-Nakashimada et al. 2023).

Our findings further confirm a mean delay of 5.33 ± 6.92 days from symptom onset to hospital admission, closely mirroring observations reported by Giannattasio et al. (2022), who described similar temporal patterns between hospitalization and the onset of liver injury, which typically preceded elevations in pancreatic enzymes. Hepatic and pancreatic involvement were common in our cohort; however, these abnormalities were generally mild, transient, and resolved with supportive care. Importantly, no cases of acute liver failure were identified.

Accumulating evidence indicates that genetic background plays a significant role in susceptibility to MIS-C. Specific HLA alleles have been associated with disease development (Sacco et al. 2022), and haploinsufficiency of SOCS1, a key negative regulator of type I and II interferon signaling, has been identified as a distinct genetic risk factor (Lee et al. 2020). In support of this, a genetic cohort study by Chou et al. (2021) reported that approximately 17% of children with MIS-C carry variants that impair the negative regulation of interferon and proinflammatory pathways, reinforcing the contribution of innate immune dysregulation to disease pathogenesis.

Looking ahead, predictive modeling of MIS-C could be substantially enhanced through hybrid analytic frameworks that integrate machine learning algorithms with classical time series approaches. Such models are particularly well suited to dynamic pandemic contexts, in which pathogen evolution, shifting population immunity, and variable healthcare responses continuously alter epidemiological patterns (Meslamani et al. 2024; Nunes et al. 2024; Zhao et al. 2024; Mohd Sofian 2025). Integrating genetic, immunological, and epidemiological data within these hybrid systems may ultimately enable more accurate risk stratification and earlier detection of MIS-C clusters.

Despite the promising predictive performance demonstrated by our ARIMA-based model, several additional limitations warrant consideration. First, the single-center design and limited sample size may restrict the generalizability of the findings. Second, the heterogeneous age distribution of participants (0–16 years) may have reduced statistical power and limited the detection of age-specific or developmental subgroup effects. Third, several observed associations did not reach statistical significance, emphasizing the need for validation in larger, multicenter cohorts. Finally, the model did not incorporate potentially influential epidemiological and immunological variables, including circulating viral variants, vaccination coverage, and demographic or socioeconomic risk factors, all of which may shape MIS-C incidence and could substantially improve model stability and predictive performance (Nirmalarajah et al. 2025). Future studies integrating these determinants into expanded datasets will be essential for strengthening the robustness, clinical utility, and real-time accuracy of MIS-C forecasting frameworks.

Conclusion

This study elucidates the temporal association between pediatric COVID-19 incidence and the subsequent development of MIS-C. Using a time series framework incorporating weekly COVID-19 case counts, we demonstrated that MIS-C incidence can be moderately predicted with a lag of approximately 5–6 weeks, a timeframe that is consistent with the postinfectious, immune-mediated pathophysiology of the syndrome. Clinically, most patients presented with pronounced abdominal and systemic inflammatory manifestations requiring multidisciplinary management; however, all children achieved full recovery, underscoring the effectiveness of timely diagnosis and appropriate treatment. Although these findings highlight the potential utility of surveillance-based forecasting for early signal detection, further research using larger, multicenter datasets and integrating additional epidemiological, virological, and clinical variables will be essential to refine predictive accuracy and strengthen public health preparedness.

Acknowledgments

Pediatric surgeons, pediatric anesthesiologists, intensive care specialists and the pediatric yard team of the UMHA-TEM “N. I. Pirogov”.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Pediatric department, University Hospital “N. I. Pirogov,” 21 “General Eduard I. Totleben” blvd; 1606 Sofia, Bulgaria.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

This study is financed by the European Union-NextGenerationEU, through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria, project № BG-RRP-2.004-0008.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, Tomov L.; Resources and literature review, Lazova S., Tzochcheva I., Miteva D., and Ali H.; Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Tomov L., Lazova S. and Velikova T.; Writing – Review & Editing, Ali H.; Supervision, Velikova T. All authors revised and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Supplementary material 1

Probability a significant ARIMA regressor loses significance after adding data

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Data type: docx

Explanation note: Target coefficient: MscL5 (regression with ARIMA(1,0,0) errors); two-sided $\alpha = 0.05$.

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Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e167298.suppl1>